

THE TAMIL MALAYALEES POLITICAL SYSTEM IN SITHER HILLS IN DHARMAPURI DISTRICT

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Our Nation India has one of the largest concentrations of Tribal population in the World. In the census report of India 2011, the Tribal population is 67.76 million, which constitutes 8.08 percent of our Nation's total population. Mostly the Tribes live in well-defined and isolated hillocks. These mountainous regions are often inaccessible and relatively under developed and poorly integrated with the rest of the nation.

Here it is worthwhile to know the meaning of the term Tribe. The term 'Tribe' derived from Roman word 'Tribua' meaning a Political Unit, or Group of People. Tribes are a group of people which possessed social institutions but not political unit.

A tribe is a social group following traditions, beliefs and customs illiberal of naturalization of ideas from alien sources. An above all a tribe is a social group conscious of a homogeneity of ethnic and territorial integration. Either they live in the relative isolation of the hills and the forests or they forced to live the above. In Tamil Nadu state, there are 36 Scheduled Tribes of which Malayalees are the largest populated community amongst Tribal communities.

Key Words: Tribal, Malayalees, Pattakkaran, Thandakaran, Village Council.

Introduction:

The Government had listed about 36 castes in Tamil Nadu State as Scheduled Tribes. Among these 36 sub castes of the scheduled tribes, the so-called Hindu Malayalee tribes are living in the villages of sitheri hills. The Malayalee tribes also living in the other places such Javathu hills, Kolli hills, Pachamalai hills, Shervaroy hills, Yelagiri hills, Bargur hills and so on.

Sitheri or **Sitteri** is a hill station in Harur taluk, Dharmapuri district, Tamil Nadu, India. It is located on the Sitheri Hills, one of the segments of the Eastern Ghats of Tamil Nadu. Sitheri is situated at an altitude of 1,097.3 metres (3,600 ft). The area comprises various vegetation types, such as the evergreen, semi-evergreen, riparian, dry deciduous bush, and southern thorn bush forests.

The minimum and maximum temperature is 19°C (66.2 °F) and 40°C (104 °F) in winter and summer, respectively. The average annual rainfall is 900 millimetres, attained from both northeast and southwest monsoons. Topographically, the area is undulating, with an altitude varying from 240 to 1,266 metres. The total area of Sitheri village is found to be 400 square kilometres, with a total population of 9,045 (4,656 male and 4,389 female) as of 2011.¹

History

The **Malayali** is a tribal group found in the Eastern Ghats of northern Tamil Nadu. The name derives from *malai-alam* meaning "**hill-place**," denoting an inhabitant of the hills. They are the largest Scheduled Tribe in Tamil Nadu, with a population of around 358,000. They are divided in to three groups: the *Periya Malayalis* ("**big**" **Malayalis**) who live in the Shevaroyes, the *Nadu Malayalis* ("**middle**" **Malayalis**) from **the Pachaimalais**, and **the Chinna Malayalis** ("**small**" **Malayalis**) from the Kollaimalais²

There are no proper historical records or books available to learn how the people migrated and settled their life at Sitheri. However, their history of migrating in the villages can be known only from the folk songs sung by them from time immemorial and from the ancient stories that are prevailing among them.

Edgar Thurston believed they were once Tamils from the plains who moved up into the hills and developed their own culture.

Each group of Malayalis has their own tales about their origins. According to their traditions, the three groups were descendants of three brothers from Kanchipuram who settled at each of the three hill ranges. One story is this: A long time ago the Vedars (hunting community) of Kagundi, having been refused marriage with Vellalar girls, kidnapped them. To recover them, seven Vellalar men set out with dogs, telling their wives that if their dogs returned alone, they should assume they had perished. At the Palar River, the men were able to cross but the dogs returned home. After the men successfully rescued the girls, they returned home to find themselves presumed dead and their wives now considered widows. Therefore they married Vedar women and moved into the hills.

Language

The mother tongue of Malayalee tribes is tamil. They do not know any other language. They have been noted as Hindu Malayalees in the Government records. The community certificate issued by the Revenue Department states them as Hindu Malayalees. Though the tribal people spread all over the country, when we say "Malayalee" most of them will right away think of the people who are living in Kerala. As the Keralites speak Malayalam, they are also termed as Malayalees. However, the tribal people speak only Tamil³. A Hill is termed as 'Malai' in Tamil and as the tribes are living and occupying forest areas in the hilly regions, they are called as Malayalees (people of hilly region). The mother tongue of the Tamil Malayalee tribes is Tamil. They do not know either to write or speak any other language other than Tamil. The people speak Tamil with their own slang and are using some different words which are not found among the Tamil speaking people of plains.

Village Council

In the social organization of the Tamil Malayalee tribes, the village council occupies an important position. The village council controls the tribal families of a particular village. Every tribal village in Sitheri has a village council. The following are the designations prevailing in their village council setup few joint families exist in Sitheri hills. Normally a big family in Sitheri hills consists of 6-8 members and a small one consists of husband and wife with single child. Big families include grand fathers and mothers in their care. After marriage most of the

men form their own family. Though these people are tilting towards a civilized life with good houses and enhanced education, still they are following some superstitious beliefs. The village council setup presides over in all the functions and ceremonies of every family in their community⁴.

Duties of Village Council

Some of the functions of Village Council are solving the problems in their village, conducting functions and ceremonies Conducting marriages, solving the problem between the husband and wife (Family feuds, Divorce cases) , solving the problems of land disputes, property disputes, problems of love marriages ,taking part in funeral and other social ceremonies, Giving punishment to perpetrators of crimes like theft, violating village codes etc. and solving problems between villages⁵.

Guru:

The **Kalasapadi**, a small village located in Sitheri Hills. This is known as “**Guru Pedam**” of Tamil Malayalees. Because in the political hierarchy Guru is the important person in this tribal group. It is the hereditary post. All Guru called themselves as “Lakshmana Guru” (the brother of god Kariramar). Only kalasapadi is the dwelling place of Guru’s. They believed the guru is the decentance of Kariraman (Perumal). All the important functions and ceremonies in the locality will be presided over by Guru⁶.

The Guru is ruled 23 Nadu. Malayalees diveided themselves their living placecs are nadu.

Powers of the Oor Goundar/ the President of Village Council

Each village has a separate Oor Goundar (President). He is the President of the village council and this designation is a hereditary one and is occupied by a particular family in succession. All the important functions and ceremonies in the locality will be presided over by Oor Goundar in the name of Guru. The village council meetings will be presided over by him. He alone has the power to take the final decision. All the people in a particular village should abide by the decisions of Oor Goundar the president of village council. The final decision taken

by the president will be unbiased and legally valuable.⁴⁰ Customs and conventions are the basis of their social system. There are no written laws or commandments for the guidance of the village council.

Manthiri Goundar (The Secretary of the Village Council)

In the chain of command, powers and functions of Village Council setup the person next to the Oor Goundar is Manthiri Goundar the secretary of the village council. He functions as an important adviser of Oor Goundar in taking most of the decisions. He will accompany the Oor Goundar in all the meetings, ceremonies, functions etc. He carries out the punishments declared by Oor Goundar. The Manthiri Gounder assists the Oor Goundar the president the president of Village Council in all the activities of the Village Council. The villagers respect him as equal to Oor Goundar. The position of Manthiri Goundar was also a hereditary one, which is occupied by a particular family in succession⁷.

The Pattakkaran (The Chief Treasurer of the Village Council)

The Pattakkaran is the Chief Treasurer of the village. He occupies the third position in hierarchy of village council. His main duties are to collect the fine amounts that are imposed by village council. He plays a very important role during the village functions and spiritual functions and holy occasions. He gets the same respect from the public as Oor Goundar and Manthiri Goundar. He can directly enquire into the problems that arose among the people and report the same to the village council. This too is a hereditary post.

The Thandakaran (The Messenger)

He is also called as *Kolkaran*. He occupies the fourth position in the village council. His service plays a major role in the proper functioning of the Village Council. He has to invite all the people of the village for all occasions of meetings and functions on behalf of village council. The people of a particular village are also the part and parcel of a village council. The **Thandakaran** also gets equal respect as other designates in Village Council⁸. This designation was also headed by a particular family in succession.

Fines for Violating Conventions

One of the unique features of Sitheri Malayalee people is that they impose penalty and collect fines if anybody violates the customs and conventions of the tribal society. In case of any theft, the person involved in the crime will be traced out by the councilors and the stolen material will be handed over the owner. The thieves involved in the crime will be fined to an extent of Rs. 100 to Rs. 500. They keep all the money so collected by way of fine as general fund and spend it for the people on the occasions of village festivities and other spiritual services⁹.

Respect to Elders

In the tribal society, elderly people were greatly respected by the younger ones. They not only show greater respect to their elderly people but also take care of the old aged without neglecting them. During marriages bride and bridegroom get the blessings from elderly people in the village. On every aspects of the life, the younger people used to consult and take the advice from the elderly people. They have the practice of getting the blessings of the elders before starting a new work either starting of a business or construction of a new house.

Changes in the Social Organisation

We find a change in the social organization of villages in the Sitheri as in the local administrative setup of towns and cities. This is because of the governmental efforts to introduce and implement the Panchayat Raj system in the country¹⁰.

Panchayat Administration

After the introduction of 73rd and 74th amendments of the constitution in 1992, Panchayat elections were conducted by most of the States throughout the country. The scheduled tribes were allotted reserved seats in the Panchayat election. The elected presidents and counsellors came to power in village Panchayats. Due of the changes introduced in the local administration of the Government, this had an impact on the traditional village setup of Sitheri region. Few changes in the administration of the tribal society also certain villages of Sitheri the

traditional heads of the village council came to occupy the various positions of Panchayat Raj system. However, even after the introduction of Panchayat system the old tribal village council occupies a superior place in the social life of the Sitheri Malayalee tribes¹¹.

The village council controls the tribal families of a particular village. Customs and conventions are the basis of their social system¹². There are no written laws or commandments for the guidance of the village council. We find a change in the social organization of villages in the Sitheri as in the local administrative setup of towns and cities. This is because of the governmental efforts to introduce and implement the Panchayat Raj system in the country.

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